

Research

Evaluating Customer Experience and Satisfaction with Robotics and AI in Hotel Services in China Using SERVQUAL

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Abstract

The tourism industry is a significant contributor to economic growth, impacting national revenue, employment, and income distribution. The global revival of tourism following the COVID-19 pandemic has promoted innovation in the hospitality sector, particularly using artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics. In China, AI-powered hotels, such as FlyZoo Hotel in Hangzhou, have implemented automated services, facial recognition check-ins, and robotic assistance to improve customer experiences. This technological shift prompts inquiries regarding customer satisfaction and acceptance of such innovations. This study evaluates the influence of AI-driven hotel services on customer experience and satisfaction using the SERVQUAL framework. By examining key service quality dimensions, including reliability, responsiveness, and assurance, the study aims to determine whether AI-powered hospitality meets or exceeds customer expectations. The findings will contribute to understanding the changing role of AI in the hotel industry and its effects on service quality and competitiveness in the post-pandemic era.

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Keywords: Tourism Industry, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Smart Hotels, Customer Satisfaction, SERVQUAL Framework, Automated Hotel Services

Introduction

It is widely acknowledged that the tourism industry is a significant contributor to the nation's overall revenue. The tourism industry ensures that investments are made in tourism businesses so that they can provide services. This, in turn, helps to reduce unemployment and distributes income to the communities that are located amidst tourism. It was reported by the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) that the tourism industry around the world is continuing to expand to an estimated 975 million tourists travelled internationally between January and September 2023, particularly as travelers resume their normal routines ("International Tourism to," 2023). It has been announced that China will no longer conduct inbound nucleic acid testing or quarantine in public areas beginning in the year 2023. After adjusting their policies in order to prevent the spread of COVID-19, major airports in many locations in China, including the metropolitan areas of Shanghai and Guangzhou, have opened their doors to welcome the first international flights. On January 8, 2023, total inbound and outbound airline ticket bookings increased by 628 percent year-over-year (YoY), marking the highest rate of expansion since March 2020. This is in line with the information that was revealed by the Tongcheng platform, which provided this information. The growth of

tourism like this has led to the vibrancy of the hotel service industry. Increasing competition and embracing tourists for staying in hotels in this New Normal era has evolved to create selling points and distinctive points for hotels to fully serve tourists, whether domestic or international.

After the outbreak of COVID-19, although the situation has returned to normal, there are some changes in conditions due to various needs and requirements. For this reason, service innovation is also driven and changed. One of them is the arrival of hotels powered by robots and operated by AI. Hotels in China are starting to pilot the transformation of their hotels into state-of-the-art services using these technologies. For example, FlyZoo Hotel in Hangzhou, the capital of Zhejiang Province, Eastern China, is equipped with artificial intelligence (AI) technology and robots, as well as an automated service system that facilitates guests' stay, lighting control, and other services. They can check in using facial recognition, which is used in place of a keycard to open the room door and access other services. Room reservations and check-out can be done through a smartphone application. Guests can control lights, televisions, and curtains in their rooms using Alibaba's voice-activated digital assistant. Meanwhile, there are robots serving as waiters for food, cocktails, tea, and coffee. Other hotels with similar functions are now available in certain areas. The incorporation of AIs and robots in hotel services raises a question for our study whether customers are satisfied with the revolutionized service innovation in these hotels.

Our study evaluates customer experience and satisfaction with robotics and AI in hotel services in China using the SERVQUAL framework.

1.1 Research Questions

1. Which SERVQUAL dimension most significantly affects overall customer satisfaction in hotels using robotics and AI?

1.2 Research Objectives

1. To assess the overall satisfaction levels of customers with hotel services using robotics and AI, using the SERVQUAL dimensions (tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy).

1.3 Significance of the Study

The study focuses on understanding customer preferences so that they can be used to shape the new landscape of the hotel and hospitality industry. The results of the study could lead to a better customer experience, goodwill, and business operations that use robots and AI in service. For service innovation, the use of robots and AI will be able to operate more efficiently from the insights gained so that they can lead to innovations for overall improvement. Hotels that successfully introduce robots and AI services will be able to differentiate themselves in a highly competitive market. The study will add to the literature on service quality and customer satisfaction and will also help add to the growing knowledge of technology and the service industry. This data can provide more insight into increasing adoption and effective technology.

By improving customer satisfaction and service quality and understanding the new form of tourism, hotel stays are of great importance in helping drive the country's economy. Hotels are one of the important factors in providing good hospitality to the guests. Tourism can be boosted if hotels are the vehicle to promote a comfortable and satisfying stay.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The target population includes hotel guests who have stayed in hotels that use robotics and AI for various services. The study will focus on hotels that incorporate robotics and AI in their services. The study will use the SERVQUAL framework to measure customer satisfaction. Data will be collected through structured questionnaires distributed to participants who have experienced robotic and AI services.

1.5 Limitation

The study may be limited by the availability and willingness of participants to complete the survey. This limitation can affect the quality and representativeness of the data collected, since the people who do participate may not fully represent the entire population of hotel guests. The sample may still not accurately reflect the true diversity of all hotel guests in China.

1.6 Definition of Key Terms

- Robotics refer to the automated machines used in hotel services, such as room service robots and cleaning robots.
- Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the use of intelligent systems in hotels, such as AI-powered concierge services and check-in kiosks.
- Customer Satisfaction refers to the satisfaction levels of hotel guests with the services provided by robotics and AI.
- SERVQUAL Framework refers to a research instrument to measure service quality across five dimensions: Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy.

Literature Review

Since 1959, people have been working on developing robots. George Devol and Joseph Engelberger are credited with developing the first robot, which was an industrial automation device. Since then, significant progress has been made in the development of industrial robots. The first robot vacuum cleaner, also known as an automatic vacuum cleaner, was manufactured by iRobot Corporation of the United States in the year 2002. This vacuum cleaner was given the name Roomba. A machine that can move around and perform its duties in a variety of settings, depending on its design, is referred to as a service robot. The mechanism of the machine is determined by the installation and programming of the machine. Apart from the use of automatic systems in industry, it can move along two axes in the x-y plane or more to conform to the environment. It can perform tasks that are beneficial for either humans or equipment. It is possible for service robots to operate in a variety of ways, including partially autonomously, in collaboration with humans, or in a fully automatic manner, without any intervention from humans.

Every brand prioritizes customers' informed purchasing decisions by delivering what they want. However, it is difficult. Due to more online sales channels, the hybrid shopping model, and higher customer expectations, creating and delivering relevant information and promotions when customers want them is harder. Therefore, businesses and brands must seek help in presenting information and promotions to customers at the right time. AI can simplify these tasks.

2.1 Hotel Industry in China

It is becoming increasingly common for humanoid robots to be utilized in real-world settings, such as in the role of hotel receptionists. Because robots are more than just machines, it is necessary to have appropriate planning in place before they can be used in a serious manner. For instance, the design of a ramp that enables the robot to lift bags in a manner that is both efficient and secure, as well as the provision of wider walkways for the purpose of ensuring the safety and convenience of guests. On the other hand, this will result in increased construction expenses. There is a significant difference between the rapid development of architecture and the rapid development of robotics, and the most significant challenge is to combine these two elements in the appropriate manner.

2.2 Service innovation and customer satisfaction

In the context of service innovation, the introduction of new ideas and methods of operation that have not been subjected to systematic thinking and an understanding of the requirements of service users is referred to as service innovation (Sundbo, 2006). This innovation serves as a guideline for the development of various services with the objective of achieving customer satisfaction. The concept is designed to provide services to customers to satisfy them, provide services to customers to the utmost, and improve and increase profits for the business by using the process of using the customer as the center, using it as a guideline for creating differentiated services (Bitner, Ostrom & Morgan, 2008). This is accomplished by providing more services to customers than ever before.

Because each type of service depends on each service provider, the quality of the service varies depending on the provider. Service time and environments while providing services also differ, with services being what service users expect and having an intangible nature. It is intangible and creates value for the products of service businesses. Therefore, businesses aim to develop services that are different from the past to respond to the needs of service users and achieve maximum satisfaction. A very important factor in creating differentiated services is "innovation," which is the source of "service innovation" in today's service business. Service innovation is mentioned as a key element in creating a competitive advantage for service businesses. The process of service innovation has an important concept from Rogers (1962) cited in Couros (2003), who created the S-curve to explain the process of diffusion of technology in society step by step to predict when society will accept technology.

For describing the effectiveness of technology, the S-curve is utilized. When new technology is invented, there are still a lot of adjustments that need to be made, and there is a need for ongoing investment. Technology will eventually reach a point of saturation, making it impossible to make any significant advancements. The more recent technological advancements will also pose a threat to it at this stage. It is possible that the efficiency of the new technology will quickly increase, potentially becoming on par with or even surpassing that of the original technology. This will occur when the new technology addresses technical problems and is continuously improved.

Mahmoud, Hinson, and Anim (2017) examine the relationship between service innovation, customer value creation (CVC), and customer satisfaction (CS) in the context of the telecommunications industry in Ghana. As a result, service innovation activities of telecommunication operators are crucial for achieving customer satisfaction. Similarly, another study by Yeh, Chen and Chen (2019) found that tourists expect tourism factories to provide more than just tourist spots; they want better services and experiences. For service innovation, developing the brand image and promoting new service concepts are more effective. The study highlights the importance of service innovation for driving customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions in the tourism factory context in Taiwan. These studies help emphasize the importance of service innovation effects on customer satisfaction.

2.3 AI in Hotel

AI algorithms can be used to analyze market trends in the field of marketing. superior information regarding competitors and the requirements of the market than humans. The adjustment of pricing and marketing strategies is significantly impacted because of this. The opportunity to generate income and increase profits is increased because of this feature. Additionally, AI can assist in the analysis of data pertaining to work and operations, which can significantly contribute to the allocation of resources.

In the meantime, technologies that are based on artificial intelligence, such as facial recognition, help make registrations go more quickly. Customers are impressed, time is saved, and unnecessary steps are reduced thanks to this feature. A safer environment for guests is created because of the ability of artificial intelligence to analyze CCTV footage. Although artificial intelligence has the potential to automate tasks, it is not yet capable of replacing all employees in the service industry.

It is also not yet capable of providing information and analyzing data efficiently and accurately. Since the hospitality and food service industries constitute an industry. The term "human-centric" refers to a business model in which customers are not merely viewed as consumers. On the other hand, the businesses must keep the customer in mind as a human being. Providing an exceptional experience for customers is still largely dependent on the employees who work for the company. Engaging in conversation with clients One must have a comprehension of feelings and emotions in order to be successful. The ability to exercise human judgment and have a comprehensive understanding of complex issues is also required when dealing with complex situations. Think of methods that lead to real solutions that artificial intelligence is unable to do.

Hotels are already widely adopting AI and robotics, especially for operational efficiency and cost savings. According to Nam et al. (2020), using AI and automation for simple, routine, and repetitive tasks can reduce costs and operational inefficiencies. Luxury hotels tend to prefer less invasive solutions. Moreover, Millauer and Vellekoop (2020) revealed that revenue management in the hospitality industry is evolving with the help of new technologies. Forecasting models using historical data have been widely used, and recent research has applied similar AI techniques to forecast hotel cancellations using PNR data, also with high accuracy (Sánchez, Sánchez-Medina & Pellejero, 2020).

2.4 Robot Services in Hotel

Although some countries are well-known for their exceptional hospitality, the level of labor productivity in those countries is quite low. Even in China, the hospitality industry has experienced a substantial decline in its workforce over the past three years (Ren, 2023). The scale of the staffing losses has been too large to feasibly replace in a short time, leading to a slow improvement of the sector. This is because certain periods of time have extended vacations, which creates difficulties in the management of appropriate manpower, particularly during times when there are many

international tourists. Therefore, the utilization of robots to accomplish the task of replacing workers will assist management in resolving this issue and will also assist in preventing employees from working excessively.

Robots are being used by businesses for a variety of reasons, including labor shortages, decreased labor efficiency because of an aging population, high labor costs, and the ability of robots to work longer hours and be more patient than human workers. Some examples of robots that are being used by businesses include robots that carry luggage, robots that provide concierge services, and robots that mow lawns. To address challenges such as labor shortages and inefficiencies, as well as rising labor costs, businesses are increasingly turning to robotic solutions. This trend is expected to continue. As a result of their ability to provide efficient and unceasing assistance in a wide range of business settings, including the transportation of luggage, the greeting of customers, and the maintenance of outdoor areas, robots have become essential tools for a great number of organizations.

Another reason why the hospitality industry in China is facing a shortage of human resources is the perspective of Chinese Confucian culture that causes people to perceive low social status or prestige of hospitality jobs compared to other professions. The study by Lv et al. (2022) revealed that undergraduates are reluctant to pursue a career in the hotel industry. There are cultural views that prioritize white-collar, office-based careers over hands-on service roles.

2.5 SERVQUAL Theoretical Framework

Service quality is a concept that has a lot of debate about its meaning and measurement, serving as the level of service that satisfies customers. SERVQUAL is a highly common instrument to analyze service quality. It may be used to evaluate the quality of services provided by hotels, banks, or hospitals, among other types of service. The year 1988 marked the beginning of the development of the SERVQUAL idea by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry. There are two components that make up the SERVQUAL idea of service quality evaluation. These components include service expectations and perceptions of certain services. Over the course of each segment, there are a total of 22 questions about services. The replies are based on a Likert scale of seven points, ranging from strongly disagreeing (one point) to strongly agreeing (seven points). However, later the adaptation of SERVQUAL showed the use of a 5-point Likert scale instead (Ibarra, Casas & Partida, 2014). Evaluation according to the SERVQUAL concept originally considered all 22 items across 10 aspects of service quality, namely appearance, reliability, responsiveness, competence, courtesy, creditability, security, access, communication, and understanding of customers. However, later studies reduced the number of service aspects to only five main dimensions. First, tangibility refers to physical characteristics that consumers can see or touch, which include measurement tools. Second, reliability refers to providing correct service, error-free, and according to the contract provided by the service provider. Third, responsiveness is a quick response and a willingness to provide services, with the ability to solve problems for service recipients quickly. Fourth, assurance comes from having service providers with knowledge, service ability, politeness, and effective communication with service recipients. Fifth, empathy towards service recipients involves being interested and attentive to service recipients, trying to understand their needs.

Regarding assessing the quality of a variety of services, such as hotel services, restaurant services, banking services, and health services (such as overall hospital services or pharmaceutical services), the use of SERVQUAL is quite helpful. SERVQUAL is a tool that assists service providers in identifying gaps in accordance with the Service Quality Model. These gaps may then be used to repair, enhance, or develop service quality in a variety of areas in order to better correspond with the expectations of the service receiver.

In the hospitality industry, there are many studies to evaluate customers' satisfaction and engagement by using the SERVQUAL model. Markovi and Raspor (2010) examined customers' perceptions of service quality in the Croatian hotel industry. The perceived service quality of hotel attributes is assessed by using a modified SERVQUAL scale. From the survey of 15 hotels in the Opatija Riviera, Croatia, hotel guests had rather high expectations regarding service quality. The result revealed that reliability and empathy were vital in their perception.

2.6 Hypotheses

H0: There is no significant impact of SERVQUAL dimensions (tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy) on overall customer satisfaction with robotics and AI in hotel services.

H1: SERVQUAL dimensions (tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy) significantly impact overall customer satisfaction.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

This framework clearly shows the relationships between the study's independent variables and dependent variables. Independent variables are the background characteristics of the respondents including three parts which are demographic information, past experiences, and prior experience with technology. The SERVQUAL dimensions are to mediate the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables as this study intends to measure various aspects of service quality provided by robotics and AI in hotels. Dependent variables are the outcomes of interest, which include overall customer satisfaction with robotics and AI services and the intention to repeat stays at hotels using these technologies.

2.7.1 Independent Variables

Section 1: Demographic Information

1. Gender:
[Male / Female / Prefer not to say / Other (please specify)]
2. Age:
[Under 18 / 18-20 / 21-23 / 24-26 / 27 or above]
3. Average Monthly Income (including part-time work and allowances):
[Below \$500 / \$501-\$1000 / \$1001-\$1500 / Above \$1500]

Section 2 :

Past experiences

- a. Frequency of Hotel Stays
[once / couple of time / often]
- b. Purpose of Stay
[Travelling / Business trip / Visiting family / Special occasions]

Prior experience

- c. How would you rate your overall comfort and proficiency with using technology?
 - i. Very Low
 - ii. Low

iii.Moderate

iv.High

v.Very High

d. How familiar are you with robotics and artificial intelligence?

i.Not at all familiar

ii.Slightly familiar

iii.Moderately familiar

iv.Very familiar

v.Extremely familiar

e. Have you had any prior experience interacting with robotics and AI in a hotel or other service industry setting?

i.Yes

ii.No

2.7.2 Mediating Variables

1. Overall satisfaction of customers using SERVQUAL

a. Tangibles

i.The service areas (lobby, rooms, dining areas) provided by the hotel are clean and comfortable.

ii.The robots used in the hotel (such as for room service or check-in) are well-maintained and presentable.

iii.The technological amenities (e.g., room controls, check-in kiosks) are easy to use and readily available.

iv.The layout and signage of the hotel make it easy to find the services I need.

b. Reliability

i.The hotel staff and robots provide services as promised without making errors.

ii.The automated and AI services (such as room service robots and check-in systems) function reliably.

iii.The services I request (such as room adjustment by AI, robotic cleaning, or maintenance) are provided promptly and as expected.

iv.The hotel staff and robots consistently follow through on their commitments, such as check-in times and room readiness.

c. Responsiveness

i.The hotel staff and robots respond promptly to my requests for assistance or services.

ii.Requests for services (such as room adjustment by AI, robotic cleaning, or maintenance) are fulfilled quickly.

iii.It is easy to get assistance when needed, whether from hotel staff or through automated systems.

d. Assurance

i.The hotel staff and automated systems make me feel confident in their ability to provide high-quality services.

ii.The hotel staff, AI and robots are knowledgeable and skilled in handling my requests and needs.

iii.The robots, AI and automated systems function smoothly and reliably, providing consistent service.

iv.The hotel staff and systems operate in an honest and transparent manner.

e. Empathy

i.The hotel staff, AI and automated systems make me feel that my individual needs and preferences are important.

ii.The hotel staff, AI and robots understand and address my specific needs effectively and efficiently.

iii.Any issues or problems I encounter are resolved in a way that feels personalized and attentive to my situation.

2.7.3 Dependent Variables

2. Customer's intention to stay at hotels using robotics and AI again (Intention to repeat)

- a. I am planning to find and stay at a hotel with robotics and AI for my next vacation due to the high level of satisfaction I experienced.
- b. The next time I visit a city that has a hotel with robotics and AI, I will choose it first because I am satisfied with the technology and services provided.
- c. If I have a chance to travel within the next year, I will choose to stay at a hotel that uses robotics and AI again because I am satisfied with the service quality.

Methodology

3.1 Data

The study focuses on hotel guests in China who have experienced services provided by robotics and AI in hotels. Random sampling was employed to ensure that the sample represents the diverse demographics of hotel guests. Regarding geography, surveys were distributed to potential participants online to fill a form with a structured questionnaire designed specifically to collect data on various factors influencing customer satisfaction and their intention to stay at hotels using robotics and AI again. The questionnaire included sections on demographic information, past experiences and technology familiarity, and perceptions of service quality using the SERVQUAL dimensions.

Dependent variables are the customer's intention to stay at hotels using robotics and AI again (intention to stay again), the customer's intention to choose hotels using robotics and AI first (intention to choose first), and the customer's intention to stay hotels using robotics and AI next year (intention to stay next year). Mediating variables in this study are five dimensions using the SERVQUAL framework to measure the overall satisfaction of hotel guests. Other independent variables are demographic information, experience, and technology familiarity. Demographic information covers only three major factors, including gender, age and average income. To determine baselines of samples, experience covers guests' frequency of hotel stays and their purpose while the questionnaires extend to ask their technology familiarity by asking their tech-savviness, their familiarity with robotics and AI, and their prior experience interacting with robotics and AI.

The process of examining and interpreting data to extract meaningful insights and information was analyzed through ordered logistic regression where is commonly used when dependent variables are based on Likert scale responses. Moreover, to reduce unstable and unreliable estimates, the model also used multicollinearity among the independent variables using VIF analysis.

3.2 Model

Ordered logistic regression is used to model the relationship between an ordinal dependent variable and one or more independent variables. The category levels of an ordinal variable are clearly ordered. Both continuous and categorical variables can be explained. Ordinal logistic regression extends logistic regression by linearly relating the logit (logging odds) of a binary response to the independent variables. K-1 logits exist if the response variable has k levels. A major assumption of ordinal logistic regression is proportional odds: an independent variable's effect is constant as the response level increases. Ordinal logistic regression outputs an intercept for each response level except one and a slope for each explanatory variable.

The parameterization of the ordinal logistic regression model is

$$\log\left(\frac{P(Y \leq j)}{1 - P(Y > j)}\right) = \alpha_j + \beta_1 \cdot x_1 + \beta_2 \cdot x_2 + \dots + \beta_p \cdot x_p, j = 2, \dots, j - 1, j$$

where $P(Y \leq j)$ is the probability that the dependent variable Y is less than or equal to category j .

α_j is the threshold parameter for category j .

$\beta_1, \beta_2 \dots + \beta_p$ are the coefficients for the independent variables.

As for the procedure of estimate,

3.2.1 Intention to Stay Again

The equation for the ordered logistic regression model predicting the intention to stay again is:

$$\log\left(\frac{\text{Intention to Stay Again} \leq j}{\text{Intention to Stay Again} > j}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{GenderDummy1} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Age} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Income} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{FreqHotelStays} + \beta_5 \cdot \text{TechComfort} + \beta_6 \cdot \text{AIFamiliarity} + \beta_7 \cdot \text{PriorAIExp} + \beta_8 \cdot \text{Tangibles} + \beta_9 \cdot \text{Reliability} + \beta_{10} \cdot \text{Responsiveness} + \beta_{11} \cdot \text{Assurance} + \beta_{12} \cdot \text{Empathy}$$

3.2.2 Intention to Choose First

The equation for the ordered logistic regression model predicting the intention to choose first is:

$$\log\left(\frac{\text{Intention to Choose First} \leq j}{\text{Intention to Choose First} > j}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{GenderDummy1} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Age} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Income} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{FreqHotelStays} + \beta_5 \cdot \text{TechComfort} + \beta_6 \cdot \text{AIFamiliarity} + \beta_7 \cdot \text{PriorAIExp} + \beta_8 \cdot \text{Tangibles} + \beta_9 \cdot \text{Reliability} + \beta_{10} \cdot \text{Responsiveness} + \beta_{11} \cdot \text{Assurance} + \beta_{12} \cdot \text{Empathy}$$

3.2.3 Intention to Stay Next Year

The equation for the ordered logistic regression model predicting the intention to stay next year is:

$$\log\left(\frac{\text{Intention to Stay Next Year} \leq j}{\text{Intention to Stay Next Year} > j}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{GenderDummy1} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Age} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Income} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{FreqHotelStays} + \beta_5 \cdot \text{TechComfort} + \beta_6 \cdot \text{AIFamiliarity} + \beta_7 \cdot \text{PriorAIExp} + \beta_8 \cdot \text{Tangibles} + \beta_9 \cdot \text{Reliability} + \beta_{10} \cdot \text{Responsiveness} + \beta_{11} \cdot \text{Assurance} + \beta_{12} \cdot \text{Empathy}$$

The overall fit of the model was assessed to indicate whether the provided models has a better fit to the data than a model with no predictors. At the same time, the pseudo R-squared value used is a measure to evaluate the proportion of variance explained by the model to ensure the model fitness. Along with this Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) helps to improve the explanatory power.

Discussion

Descriptive analysis

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Table

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics Table

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Female	58	52.25
	Male	51	45.95
	Other	2	1.8
Age	Under 18	1	0.9
	18-20	11	9.91
	21-23	17	15.32
	24-26	62	55.86
	27 or above	20	18.02
Income	Below \$500	32	28.83

	\$501-\$1000	25	22.52
	\$1001-\$1500	31	27.93
	Above \$1500	23	20.72
Frequency of Hotel Stays	Once	15	13.51
	Couple of times	37	33.33
	Often	59	53.15
Purpose of Stay	Travelling	76	68.47
	Business trip	14	12.61
	Visiting family	8	7.21
	Special occasions	13	11.71

Most respondents are female (52.25%), but the proportion of male participants was not significantly lower (45.95%). The most common age group is 24-26 (55.86%). The second largest group was 27 or above (18.02%), followed by 21-23 (15.32%). A significant portion of respondents have an income below \$500 (28.83%). The second largest group was those earning \$1001-\$1500 (27.93%). The largest group stays often (53.15%), with fewer staying a couple of times (33.33%) and the least staying once (13.51%). Most respondents travel for leisure (68.47%), with business trips and other purposes being less common.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics for Variables

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics for Variables

Variable	Observations	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
TechComfort	111	3.964	0.725	1	5
AI Familiarity	111	3.613	0.906	1	5
Tangibles	111	4.237	0.738	1	5
Reliability	111	4.078	0.823	1	5
Responsiveness	111	4.212	0.782	1	5
Assurance	111	4.213	0.787	1	5
Empathy	111	4.167	0.872	1	5

On average, the respondents feel relatively comfortable with technology with the mean score of 3.964. There is some variability in the level of comfort with technology among the respondents with a standard deviation of 0.725 after giving participants to rate from 1 to 5. The respondents have a moderate level of familiarity with AI with the average familiarity with AI of 3.613. There is some diversity in the level of AI familiarity among the respondents with a standard deviation of 0.906. The respondents are highly satisfied with the physical aspects of the service with the average score of 4.237 for the tangibles dimension. There is relatively little variability in the respondents' perceptions of the tangibles with the standard deviation of 0.738. The respondents generally find the services to be dependable with the mean score of 4.078 for reliability. There is some variation in the respondents' perceptions of the reliability of the services with the standard deviation of 0.823. The respondents feel the service is prompt and helpful with the high mean score of 4.212 for the responsiveness dimension. There is moderate variability in the respondents' perceptions of the service's responsiveness with the standard deviation of 0.782. The respondents have a high level of confidence and trust in the service with the mean score of 4.213 for the assurance dimension. There is some variation in the respondents' perceptions of the assurance provided by the service with the standard deviation of 0.787. The respondents feel the service provides a strong sense of personalized attention and care with the average score of 4.167 for the empathy dimension. There is relatively more variability in the respondents' perceptions of the empathy dimension compared to some of the other dimensions with the standard deviation of 0.872.

4.3 Basic regression results

This study develops three models predicting different aspects of customer behavior related to their intention to stay at a hotel. The models are:

1. Intention to Stay Again

This model examines the factors that make customers want to come back and stay at the hotel again.

2. Intention to Choose First

This model focuses on what makes customers choose this hotel as their top choice when deciding where to stay.

3. Intention to Stay Next Year

This model examines factors influencing the likelihood that a customer will choose to stay at the hotel in the following year.

Each model has a different aspect of customer behavior, such as their intention to return, their preference for the hotel, and their likelihood of staying next year. Using multiple models ensures that various dimensions of customer intentions are captured in order to give the hotels a more well-rounded and comprehensive understanding of their customers. Moreover, as a single model might overlook specific nuances and complexities of customer behavior, this approach improves the reliability and validity of the predictions. This study therefore uses three separate ordered logistic regression models to predict the intention to stay again, the intention to choose the hotel first, and the intention to stay next year. The models include independent and mediating variables. The first variable, GenderDummy1, is a binary or dummy variable that represents the gender of the respondents. The Age variable simply represents the age of the respondents. The Income variable reflects the income level of the respondents. Higher-income individuals may have different preferences and expectations compared to those with lower incomes. The FreqHotelStays variable measures the frequency of hotel stays or visitation by the respondents. The TechComfort variable represents the respondents' level of comfort and familiarity with technology. The AIFamiliarity and PriorAIExp variables are related to the respondents' awareness and prior experience with artificial intelligence (AI) technology. As for SERVQUAL, the Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy variables represent different aspects of the hotel service quality, potentially influencing customer intentions and preferences.

Table 3 Basic regression results

Variable	Intention to Stay Again	Intention to Choose First	Intention to Stay Next Year
GenderDummy1	0.837 (0.387)	1.261 (0.644)	1.679 (0.837)
Age	0.811 (0.214)	1.460 (0.427)	1.211 (1.211)
Income	1.042 (0.217)	0.697 (0.169)	0.958 (0.214)
FreqHotelStays	0.839 (0.317)	0.699 (0.314)	0.641 (0.261)
TechComfort	1.281 (0.439)	0.646 (0.243)	1.089 (0.411)
AIFamiliarity	0.951 (0.242)	1.303 (0.367)	0.990 (0.260)
PriorAIExp	0.540 (0.389)	0.826 (0.639)	0.331 (0.256)
Tangibles	0.867 (0.472)	2.069 (1.253)	0.818 (0.483)

Reliability	1.740 (0.815)	1.912 (0.943)	1.643 (0.846)
Responsiveness	1.008 (0.490)	2.240 (1.184)	2.354 (1.259)
Assurance	2.905* (1.597)	1.394 (0.816)	1.215 (0.661)
Empathy	2.492** (1.080)	3.485** (1.586)	5.010** (2.44)

Notes: Significance Levels

* $p < 0.1$

** $p < 0.05$

*** $p < 0.01$

The statistical significance of the coefficients is indicated by asterisks, with * representing $p < 0.1$ and ** representing $p < 0.05$.

The regression coefficients are presented along with the standard errors, which represent the strength and direction of the relationship between customer intention and various independent variables from demographic factors to previous experience to five dimensions of the SERVQUAL model.

The finding revealed that out of five dimensions, only empathy shows a statistical significance at the confidence of 95% for all three models with different dependent variables, including intention to stay again, choosing the hotel first, and staying next year. Empathy in this study refers to the ability of hotel staff, AI, and automated systems to recognize and respond to the individual needs, preferences, and experiences of guests. The percentage increase in the odds corresponding to an odds ratio can be calculated by finding the percentage of the odds ratio minus one.

Empathy is a significant predictor of the intention to stay again at the 5% level. The odds ratio of 2.492 for empathy indicates that a one-unit increase in perceived empathy of the hotel services (including robotics and AI) leads to an approximately 149.2% increase in the odds of a higher intention to stay again.

While assurance also shows a strong effect, with a 190.5% increase in the odds of a higher intention to stay again for a one-unit increase, this effect is only significant at the 10% level ($p = 0.052$). This assurance relationship has a lower level of confidence. This suggests that the relationship between the empathy dimension and the dependent variable that participants intended to stay again at robotics- and AI-incorporating hotels in China is a more consistent and robust predictor of customer intentions to stay again compared to the relationship of assurance.

Empathy has a significant positive effect on the intention to choose the hotel first, with an odds ratio of 3.485. A one-unit increase in perceived empathy of the hotel services with robotics and AI leads to an approximately 248.5% increase in the odds of the customer choosing the hotel first.

In the third model, empathy has a highly significant positive effect on the intention to stay next year, with an odds ratio of 5.010. A one-unit increase in perceived empathy of the hotel services, including robotics and AI, leads to an approximately 401.0% increase in the odds of the customer staying at the hotel next year.

Therefore, empathy, even in the context of technology-enabled services, is a crucial factor in driving positive customer outcomes. Other variables show varying levels of influence but No independent variables are statistically significant at either confidence of 99%, 95% and 90%.

4.4 Robustness check

Model Summary:

Number of observations: 111

LR chi2(12): 71.50

Prob > chi2: 0.0000

Log likelihood: -92.483508

Pseudo R2: 0.2788

Ordered Logistic Regression (Ologit) is tested with the iterative process and convergence. The final log likelihood value is -92.483508. With this negative sign, the likelihood function is less than 1, as likelihood values are always between 0 and 1. The model has converted to a set of parameter values that provide a reasonably good fit to the data. With the value of LR $\chi^2(12) = 71.50$ and the associated p-value of $\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$, the model is statistically significant. As the p-value is less than 0.001 which is highly significant, the model is robust and can be considered a good fit to the data. With the pseudo-R-squared value of 0.2788, the model explains approximately 27.88% of the variation in the dependent variable. It is generally considered a reasonable level of explanatory power. The model converging within five iterations indicates a stable solution, which is a positive sign.

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) measures the multicollinearity among the independent variables. Normally, a VIF value greater than 10 indicates high multicollinearity. This was found in the former model that includes gender dummies for males, females and those who prefer not to say. However, with all these dummies, there is a moderate-to-high multicollinearity among the independent variables with the mean VIF at 4.63 (Appendix 1.). This can inflate the variance of the coefficient estimates, leading to removing the problematic variables and re-calculating the VIF to ensure multicollinearity is adequately addressed.

Table 4 Robustness check

Variable	Intention to Stay Again		Intention to Choose First		Intention to Stay Next Year	
	VIF	1/VIF	VIF	1/VIF	VIF	1/VIF
Assurance	4.71	0.212154	4.71	0.212154	4.71	0.212154
Tangibles	4.44	0.225103	4.44	0.225103	4.44	0.225103
Reliability	4.03	0.24786	4.03	0.24786	4.03	0.24786
Responsiveness	3.76	0.266211	3.76	0.266211	3.76	0.266211
Empathy	3.63	0.275137	3.63	0.275137	3.63	0.275137
FreqHotelStays	1.67	0.599017	1.67	0.599017	1.67	0.599017
TechComfort	1.55	0.644739	1.55	0.644739	1.55	0.644739
Income	1.42	0.706357	1.42	0.706357	1.42	0.706357
PriorAExp	1.38	0.724863	1.38	0.724863	1.38	0.724863
GenderDummy1	1.35	0.740075	1.35	0.740075	1.35	0.740075
AIFamiliarity	1.33	0.750651	1.33	0.750651	1.33	0.750651
Age	1.32	0.75482	1.32	0.75482	1.32	0.75482
	Mean VIF	2.55	Mean VIF	2.55	Mean VIF	2.55

After the re-evaluation of the independent variables, the mean VIF has improved to 2.55 which is acceptable. The predictor variables are not highly correlated with each other. The model's coefficient estimates are likely to be stable and reliable, and the statistical inferences made based on the model are more trustworthy. To ensure the stability and reliability of the ordered logistic regression models predicting three different dependent variables– Intention to Stay Again, Intention to Choose First, and Intention to Stay Next Year– likelihood ratio chi-square test shows that the models are statistically significant, and R-squared values indicate the proportion of variability explained by the models. The model is also simplified to provide stable and reliable predictions for the dependent variables.

Conclusion

The study investigated the factors from various demographic to technology-related to service quality factors, influencing three different dependent variables: the respondents' intention to stay at the hotel again in the future, intention to choose this hotel as their first choice for future stays, and intention to stay at the hotel in the following year. The main finding revealed that empathy was consistently significant across all models. This means that customers who perceive higher empathy from the hotel's staff and services are more likely to have positive intentions towards the hotel. Assurance was significant for one model. Assurance showed a positive and significant effect. This shows that higher levels of

assurance in the hotel's services increase the likelihood of customers intending to stay again. However, demographic factors and prior experiences with AI and technology comfort do not strongly influence the customers' intentions in the context of this study.

As for the recommendations, training hotel staff to be more empathetic and responsive to individual customer needs can help create a more positive and memorable customer experience. To be specific, training AI and robots through the right algorithms, pre-programmed to respond naturally and empathetically, can encourage positive feelings and increase the likelihood of returning guests. If a hotel has the resources, additional investments in quality assurance can inspire confidence in customers, resulting in a positive return on their stay.

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Appendix

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
GenderDummy1	30.52	0.032761
GenderDummy2	28.86	0.034652
Responsiveness	5.41	0.184934
Assurance	5.08	0.196784
TechComfort	5.07	0.197132
Reliability	5	0.199937
AI Familiarity	4.82	0.207478
Reliability	4.7	0.212865
Empathy	4.57	0.218606
Tangibles	4.51	0.221539
StayPurpose1	4.44	0.224994
Empathy	4.24	0.235984
Assurance	4.18	0.239393
Tangibles	3.93	0.25419
AI Familiarity	3.84	0.260737
Reliability	3.71	0.269605
Responsiveness	3.42	0.291994
Reliability	3.39	0.294814
Tangibles	3.29	0.304336
Assurance	3.28	0.304423
Tangibles	3.23	0.309708
StayPurpose2	3.23	0.309775
Assurance	3.14	0.31837
Responsiveness	3.09	0.32363
Income	3.06	0.326795
AI Familiarity	2.84	0.351545
StayPurpose3	2.69	0.371512
Empathy	2.64	0.378449
Age	2.6	0.384164
TechComfort	2.58	0.387169
FreqHotelStays	2.57	0.38835
TechComfort	2.54	0.394379
FreqHotelStays	2.52	0.396608
Income	2.48	0.403603
Age	2.48	0.403666
Age	2.36	0.424511
Income	2.34	0.427079
TechComfort	1.93	0.518476
PriorAIExp	1.89	0.52968
AI Familiarity	1.83	0.547107
Age	1.51	0.660437

